

Microreactor Control Drum Decussing Model in MPACT

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we describe a new approach in MPACT for performing decussing of control drums for microreactor analysis. The method employs an equivalent 1D problem of the control drum circumferential region solved as a fixed source discrete ordinates problem. The solution of this transport problem is used as an approximation of the true scalar flux to perform flux-volume weighting to homogenize the tips of the absorbers in the control drums. This approach is evaluated against volume-weighted homogenization for a 2D microreactor core, using OpenMC and an explicitly discretized MPACT simulation as references. Results show that the proposed method effectively mitigates the cusping effect with only 90 azimuthal sectors in full core simulations. Maximum Δk bias reduces from 384 pcm to 113 pcm, while the RMS pin power difference improves from 0.95% to 0.17% across all control drum positions. The runtime overhead of the solving 1D transport problem is negligible.

Keywords: decussing, microreactor, control drum, MPACT

1. INTRODUCTION

Control rod or drum decussing is fundamentally a correction to a homogenization error. The cusping problem arises because a material boundary between a strongly absorbing material and other material (usually a moderator) does not perfectly align with a mesh boundary. For the spatial cell that must homogenize the tip of the control material with the non-control material, the correct approach is to do flux-volume weighting. However, the usual problem of requiring knowledge of the solution to do the homogenization to obtain the solution prevents one from doing so. Therefore, the simplest solution is to only do volume weighting when homogenizing. Computing the homogenized cross section via volume weighting is equivalent to assuming a uniform flux distribution across the spatial cell. The result of this assumption is that the absorption in the homogenized cross section is overestimated because the true flux solution will invariably be reduced in the absorber due to spatial self-shielding effects of the absorber.

Historically, numerous methods have been developed to address the cusping problem [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. The basic idea in many of these approaches is to precompute a correction factor for the volumetric weighting by running simplified, yet representative, problems. These correction factors are usually tabulated or represented as polynomials that are a function of the normalized depth of the control material within a spatial cell. Other common approaches are to construct a simplified transport problem to compute an estimate of the flux within the spatial cell to use as an additional weighting function in the homogenization. Either approach can be suitable across a range of applications.

In MPACT [8, 9], we have traditionally used the polynomial approach for Light Water Reactor (LWR) analysis where a separate polynomial is precomputed for each control rod type, e.g., B₄C rods, AIC rods, W rods, and AIC rods with B₄C tips. Recently, University of Michigan has been extending the

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capabilities of MPACT to be able to simulate heat-pipe cooled microreactors [10, 11]. Since microreactors frequently include a control drum, instead of a control rod, additional geometric capabilities were implemented to model these. For calculations that perform a critical drum search or transient calculations, we do not know *a priori*, how exactly each drum will be rotated. As a result, we expect to have spatial cells that homogenize the control drum absorber material with the rest of the drum material. This necessarily requires the implementation of a decussing method.

In the remainder of this paper we describe the decussing methodology newly implemented to perform decussing on the control drums. Then we present numerical results to assess the accuracy and sensitivities of the decussing method. The problem studied is a 2D microreactor core with 12 control drums based on [12]. The reference results are generated from OpenMC [13] and MPACT with an explicitly discretized mesh. At the end we give a summary and conclusions of the work.

2. DECUSPING METHODOLOGY

As briefly mentioned in the previous section, regions where the drum absorber and reflector overlap use a homogenized material composition which should be flux-volume weighted.

In the case of Finite Element Method (FEM) based diffusion or transport codes, multiple cross sections can be incorporated into the basis functions of FEM, allowing for a more natural representation of the overlapped regions [14, 6]. However, this approach is not available in the Method of Characteristics (MOC) used in MPACT.

Instead, we devise a method to estimate the flux in the region where the drum absorber and reflector overlap, to obtain a more accurate weighting function for the flux. We then use (an estimated) flux-volume weighting procedure to homogenize the cross section in these regions. In this method, the control drum absorber region is transformed into an equivalent 1D problem, as depicted in Figure 1. The 1D problem uses periodic boundary conditions at both sides of problem boundary. The first macro region is filled with reflector, the other region is filled with absorber.

Figure 1. 1D problem for control drum decussing method

For this problem, the following 1D S_N transport equation is solved with a unit source for each energy group:

$$\mu_m \frac{\partial \psi_{m,g}(x)}{\partial x} + \Sigma_{tr,g}(x) \psi_{m,g}(x) = s, \quad (1)$$

$$\phi_g(x) = \frac{\sum_m w_m \psi_{m,g}(x)}{\sum_m w_m}, \quad (2)$$

where μ_m is the cosine of the discretized angle index m ; $\psi_{m,g}(x)$ is the angular flux for angle μ_m , energy group g , and position x ; $\Sigma_{tr,g}(x)$ is the macroscopic transport cross section; s is a fixed source (here, $s = 1$ for all energy groups and regions); $\phi_g(x)$ is the scalar flux, calculated by integrating the angular flux over all angles.

To reduce spatial discretization error in the solution of the 1D problem, each macro region is further subdivided with a spatial submesh, which is dynamically set as the maximum of 90 or the user-defined number of azimuthal sectors. The equation is solved using the NEM- S_N kernel available in MPACT [8], which employs cubic Legendre polynomials for the internal spatial flux representation within each submesh. Once the solution is obtained by solving Equations (1) and (2), the homogenized cross section at any location in the control absorber/reflector ring can be calculated as follows:

$$\Sigma_{g,i} = \frac{\int_{x_1}^{x_2} \Sigma_g(x) \phi_g(x) dx}{\int_{x_1}^{x_2} \phi_g(x) dx}, \quad (3)$$

where $\Sigma_g(x)$ is the cross section for any reaction type at location x and energy group g ; x_1 and x_2 are the relative positions corresponding to the target angular location in the original problem; $\Sigma_{g,i}$ is the resultant homogenized cross section; and $\phi_g(x)$ is the solution from the 1D transport problem.

The main assumptions underlying this approach are as follows:

- The unit source is assumed to represent incoming neutrons from outside the control drum ring.
- The scattering source within the corresponding ring region is considered less important than the neutron source originating from the core and other reflector regions.
- Only a minimal level of accuracy is required to calculate the internal flux in the control drum absorber/reflector overlapped region, once the mesh size is sufficiently small due to the azimuthal sectors.

The 1D S_N transport problem does not include group-to-group interactions since a fixed source is used in Equation (1); therefore, the solution process requires only a few tens of iterations to converge. For a 252-group calculation with 120 submeshes and 8 angles in the range $0-\pi$, the runtime for a single drum calculation using one CPU core is 0.075 seconds.

MPACT employs domain decomposition for 2D core calculations, so an increase in the number of drums is not an issue, as only the drums included in each partition are considered in the calculation. There is significant potential for further optimization of the 1D problem, such as reducing the number of submeshes by varying mesh sizes according to importance; however, since the current runtime performance is sufficient, further improvements will be pursued as needed.

The 1D approach performs homogenization along the transverse direction of the absorber thickness; consequently, dependency on the thickness is minimized. While some sensitivity may exist, it is expected to be negligible for standard microreactor designs and will be investigated in future work.

In the future, once thermal feedback is available to calculate the control drum temperature and control drum isotopic depletion is performed, the 1D equation will need to be solved repeatedly. However, compared to the computational burden of other transport and cross section calculations, this is not expected to be a significant issue.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. Problem Description

The example problem used in this study is the eVinciTM motivated design (EMD) 2D core problem [12], as shown in Figure 2. In this figure, 120 azimuthal sectors are used in the control drum absorber regions. Each azimuthal sector corresponds to a distinct cross section region, allowing for straightforward indexing to replace the material and cross section depending on the control drum rotation.

The number of sectors can be specified by the user; by default, 120 sectors are generated for annular rings containing partially spanned geometries, such as a control drum, as illustrated in Figure 2b. In the case of the EMD core problem, this level of azimuthal division results in approximately 5 additional

cross section regions for each pin-cell overlapped with the control drum in the reflector regions. While this increases the number of cross section regions, it does not pose a significant computational burden. This is because each pin-cell in the fuel assembly already utilizes roughly 6 cross section regions due to radial divisions in the fuel compacts, as well as two to three additional regions in the moderator to account for fuel isotopic depletion and temperature profile variations from thermal feedback calculations.

Figure 2. Geometry and mesh regions of EMD 2D core problem

The number of fine source regions also increases with azimuthal divisions; however, the fine source region mesh is already very fine in order to reduce spatial discretization error of the source in the transport calculation. A reflector pin-cell far from the core region uses approximately 60 fine source regions, while a pin-cell overlapped with the drum absorber has about 5 more source regions. Overall, the total number of fine source regions increases from 566,178 (without submesh) to 582,270 (with 120 azimuthal sectors), which represents less than a 3% increase in the total number of spatial mesh regions.

In this study, MPACT simulations used the standard modeling options, including the ENDF/B-VII.1 51-group library [15] that was developed for standard LWR analysis, the flat source approximation, and transport corrected P_0 scattering. The MOC discretization parameters used are the number of azimuthal sectors in the control drum circumferential ring region. The OpenMC calculations utilized 200,000 neutrons per cycle, with 5000 active cycles and 200 inactive cycles. The standard deviations of

the OpenMC reference were less than 3 pcm for k_{eff} and 0.15% for the pin power tallies.

The 2D EMD core was analyzed by uniformly rotating all twelve control drums in 1° increments, ranging from 0° (fully inserted) to 180° (fully withdrawn). To isolate the bias introduced by multi-group cross-section generation and resonance self-shielding, an MPACT simulation with an explicitly discretized mesh (360 azimuthal sectors) is used as the deterministic reference (MPACT-360). Since this solution eliminates the drum absorber/reflector overlapped region, it enables us to evaluate the effectiveness of the decussing method independent of the discrepancies between the Monte Carlo and deterministic code.

3.2. Results

Figure 3 compares the Δk results of the implemented decussing method and volume-weighted homogenization relative to the OpenMC reference. In both scenarios, the maximum observed Δk occurs when the control drums are half-withdrawn (90°). However, the decussing treatment substantially lowers the Δk magnitude across all azimuthal mesh refinements and drum positions.

Figure 4 plots the RMS pin power differences as a function of the drum rotation. These discrepancies similarly peak at around 90°, likely due to the control drum having the highest differential rod worth at this position. Table I summarizes the maximum errors in k_{eff} and pin power results across all control drum rotations.

Figure 3. Δk relative to OpenMC for EMD 2D core.

(a) Decussing treatment

(b) Volume-weighted treatment

Figure 4. RMS pin power difference relative to OpenMC for EMD 2D core.

 Table I. Maximum Δk and pin power differences for EMD 2D core.

Azimuthal Sectors (N)	Method	Max Δk (pcm)		RMS diff (%)		Max diff (%)	
		OpenMC	MPACT-360	OpenMC	MPACT-360	OpenMC	MPACT-360
30	Decussed	573	566	1.43	1.50	6.01	5.99
	Volume-weighted	1326	1335	3.53	3.59	14.08	14.12
60	Decussed	178	165	0.39	0.42	1.76	1.73
	Volume-weighted	622	621	1.61	1.67	6.87	6.91
90	Decussed	113	65	0.17	0.17	0.85	0.69
	Volume-weighted	384	378	0.95	1.02	4.18	4.22
120	Decussed	113	26	0.15	0.07	0.69	0.29
	Volume-weighted	263	254	0.63	0.68	2.83	2.84
150	Decussed	112	10	0.15	0.03	0.65	0.11
	Volume-weighted	231	224	0.54	0.60	2.45	2.51
360	Explicit	113	-	0.15	-	0.61	-

3.3. Discussion

Relative to the explicitly discretized MPACT reference, the volume-weighted approach shows a large Δk of 1335 pcm at $N=30$, which reduces to 378 pcm and 224 pcm at $N=90$ and $N=150$, respectively. In contrast, the decussing method sees Δk of only 566 pcm at $N=30$, which decreases to a negligible 65 pcm at $N=90$ and 10 pcm at $N=150$. When compared to OpenMC, the decussed solution achieves Δk of

113 pcm at $N=90$, which matches the inherent bias between the MPACT reference and the Monte Carlo solution. This indicates that the decussing treatment effectively mitigates the cusping effect when finer azimuthal discretizations are used.

A similar trend is observed in the pin power differences. At $N=90$, the decussing method reduces the RMS difference from 0.95% to 0.17% relative to the OpenMC reference. This value closely aligns with the OpenMC statistical uncertainty of 0.15%, confirming a high level of accuracy in the MPACT pin power distribution. Overall, these findings suggest that the proposed decussing method effectively mitigates the cusping effect in control drum modeling for microreactor analysis, provided that at least 90 azimuthal sectors are used.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a new decussing approach for modeling control drums in MPACT for microreactor analysis. By solving an equivalent 1D fixed-source discrete ordinates problem within the control drum circumferential region, the method provides a physically informed flux approximation for the homogenization of the absorber material. Verification against a 2D microreactor core problem demonstrates that cusping effect becomes negligible when employing at least 90 azimuthal sectors.

At this discretization level, the maximum discrepancy in k_{eff} is 113 pcm, with an RMS pin power difference of 0.17%. These results are consistent with the inherent biases observed when comparing deterministic to Monte Carlo solution. Future work will involve optimizing the spatial submesh in the 1D problem and investigating the sensitivity of the results to the absorber thickness.

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